

Cheating or chatting: Teaching with AI in Higher Education

Marina De Rossi¹[0000-0002-5115-8196] and Carlo Mariconda²[0000-0002-8215-9394]

¹ University of Padua, Department of Philosophy, Sociology, Education and Applied Psychology

Padova, ITALY – marina.derossi@unipd.it

² University of Padua, Department of Mathematics “Tullio Levi-Civita”, Padova, ITALY – carlo.mariconda@unipd.it

Abstract. In this paper, we describe how we used a discipline-specific chatbot in two university courses—Foundations of Analysis and Probability (FAMP) and Cryptography—to promote critical AI literacy. Recent studies on generative AI (GenAI) emphasize both its potential for improving learning and the concerns regarding ethics, academic integrity, and possible algorithmic bias. By developing a “Tutor FAMP” chatbot specifically for our course material, we introduced two main activities—a peer review task and an error-spotting assignment—so that students could document, reflect on, and correct the AI-generated content. Our observations show that, when students are guided to analyze chatbot outputs, they become more aware of factual limits or so-called “hallucinations,” leading to gains in subject comprehension and critical thinking. Instead of prohibiting GenAI, we propose a strategy based on transparent documentation and ethical use of AI. We believe this approach can help adapt teaching methods and assessment practices in an era where GenAI is constantly expanding, preparing learners more effectively for the realities of a world increasingly influenced by advanced AI technologies.

Keywords: Critical AI Literacy, Chatbots, Generative AI.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

In recent years, scientific interest has intensified in generative Artificial Intelligence (GenIA) systems (Cao et al., 2023) applied to educational contexts (Jiang et al., 2022; Chan, 2023) both for the understanding and creation of new textual forms, and as a means of communication and interaction for the production of meaning (Sperling et al., 2024).

The aim is to offer new generations the opportunity to acquire skills to learn critically and responsibly in a world in which AI plays an increasingly important role, but which

must be approached with attention to human values, equity and inclusion (*Agenda 2030, Goal 4 'Quality Education'*) and ethics (Unesco, 2021).

In this context, it is essential to focus the analysis on technological application models, such as chatbots or conversational agents (CA), which offer specific functionalities useful in teaching-learning contexts (Zhou et al., 2020).

Numerous studies highlight the advantages of using chatbots in teaching and learning processes (Deng & Yu, 2023), such as: enabling real-time interactions and improving communication skills among peers (Okonkwo & Ade-Ibijola, 2021), encourage interaction (Yin et al., 2024) increase the efficiency of student learning (Wu et al., 2020), support the motivation to plan and evaluate one's learning path (Gabrielli et al., 2020).

In particular, in e-learning or blended learning contexts chatbot-supported learning can have a positive impact on knowledge acquisition (Ait Baha et al., 2024), student engagement and motivation (Chang et al., 2022), and self-regulation and autonomy in learning (Han et al., 2022).

However, although from one point of view these artificial intelligence tools offer unprecedented opportunities to improve teaching and learning, from another they raise critical concerns regarding ethics (Kooli, 2023), the risks of algorithmic bias (Birenbaum, 2023; Sullivan & McLaughlan, 2023) and the need for specific critical literacy skills for critical and responsible use (Kerneža, 2023).

A widespread fear is that with easy access to GenIA resources, such as ChatGPT, the principles of fairness in assessment could be violated (Cotton et al., 2024) due to the lack of reliable AI detection tools (Lodge et al., 2023) and adequate regulation and guidelines (Chan, 2023). There are also widespread concerns about the lack of AI training for university teachers and students (Chan, 2023).

The new scenario is very complex, so it is not always easy to find the dividing line between what is admissible and what is not regular. These crucial issues not only highlight the importance of reviewing key concepts in assessment (e.g., the security and validity of assessment), but also emphasise the need to redesign assessment methodologies in higher education to better prepare students for a world with AI (Luo, 2024).

1.2 Aim of the paper

The present paper describes a pair of instructional activities undertaken in two university courses—*Foundations of Analysis and Probability (FAMP)* (second year of the Bachelor's degree in Computer Engineering) and *Cryptography (master degree in Cybersecurity)* both of the University of Padova—to foster critical AI literacy. Specifically, our goals are:

1. To encourage students to critically evaluate AI-generated responses, recognizing both their strengths and limitations.
2. To situate AI usage within an evolving framework of academic integrity—one that stresses transparent documentation and informed reflection.

By deliberately guiding students to identify, discuss, and even correct chatbot “hallucinations,” we propose a pragmatic and ethically grounded approach to teaching with (and about) AI in higher education.

2 Backgrounds and Literature

2.1 Chatbots in Education

The Okonkwo & Ade-Ibijola (2021) offer a comprehensive review of chatbots in various instructional contexts, underscoring their potential to provide one-on-one tutoring, relieve faculty workload, and expand flexible learning opportunities. However, research also warns about overreliance on AI tools, factual errors (often called hallucinations), and the risk of a “copy-paste culture” if students view AI-generated answers as infallible.

2.2 Academic Integrity: Evolving Conceptions of Plagiarism

Plagiarism is commonly defined as presenting someone else’s words or ideas as one’s own without proper attribution. Yet, as Eaton (2021, 2023) points out, plagiarism becomes more complex in an era where *all* professional writing is arguably “hybrid”—that is, partially AI-assisted. Traditional enforcement measures may fail to address the educational dimension of how (and why) students should develop agency and critical thinking when using AI.

2.3 AI Literacy as a 21st-Century Skill

Influential institutions have recognized AI literacy as a core competency for contemporary learners. Luiss University recently mandated AI coursework for all Master’s students. Similarly, a new MOOC titled “Imparare con l’IA” (Sancassani, Casiraghi, & Baldoni, 2025) aims to help students collaborate effectively with AI while maintaining ethical and scholarly standards. These initiatives echo broader calls for embedding critical digital and AI literacy within university curricula (Binkley et al., 2012).

3 Methodology and Course Context

3.1 Courses

Two courses served as the testing ground for our activities:

1. Foundations of Analysis and Probability (FAMP)

- Second-year undergraduate course in Computer Engineering (blended format)
- Approximately 600 students (4 different channels)

2. Cryptography

- Graduate-level course in a Master’s program on Cybersecurity
- Approximately 100 students

Both activities were supervised by Carlo Mariconda who was also coordinator of FAMP channels and instructor of both courses and were a part of the formative assessment for students who participated to the “follower’s path”¹.

3.2 The “Tutor FAMP” and “Tutor Crypto” Chatbots

For the FAMP course, we built a custom chatbot, referred to as “Tutor FAMP,” using ChatGPT Plus but fine-tuned with materials tailored to the course—lecture notes, problem sets, and slides. Tutor FAMP could answer queries on *analysis* and *probability* topics but, like any AI system, occasionally produced inaccurate or misleading outputs. Similarly, a chatbot “Tutor Crypto” was built upon the material of the Cryptography course.

Example of Hallucination. A notable case involved a student asking whether a non-constant plane curve with *constant modulus* (i.e., all points on the curve are at a fixed distance from a single point) could be anything besides a circle. The chatbot confidently replied, “Yes, here is an ellipse example,” fabricating a scenario in which an ellipse maintained constant distance from a single focal point—blatantly incorrect. This instance illustrated the hallucination phenomenon, wherein the model combined fragments of geometry concepts to produce an authoritative-sounding yet false statement.

¹In Italy, students are permitted to participate in at least five exam sessions throughout the academic year; adopting the recommended study path encourages them to take the exams at the earliest opportunity.

4 Activities

4.1 Activity 1: Error-Spotting Task

Objective: Encourage students to evaluate and, if necessary, correct AI-generated answers, thereby reinforcing the notion that AI outputs are not automatically authoritative.

1. Prompt with an Error

Students submitted at least one prompt to the chatbot designed to elicit an *ambiguous* or *incorrect* response. Students were asked not to invent tricky questions and not to try to confuse the chatbot *intentionally*.

2. Student Corrections

They then identified inaccuracies, explaining the correct reasoning or data. For instance, if the chatbot gave a flawed probability formula, the student would show the correct version, highlighting the AI's mistake.

3. Submission

Students documented their “prompt–response–correction” sequence in a brief written report or presentation slide through a *homework activity* in Moodle. They were asked to reflect on why the chatbot might have erred and how they identified the issue.

4. Evaluation

This exercise was formatively assessed (partial course credit), aiming more to build skills than heavily impact final grades.

Participation Levels

- FAMP: 60 comprehensive submissions out of ~600 students
- Cryptography: 24 submissions out of ~100 students

While participation was modest, those who engaged demonstrated deeper analytical awareness of AI limitations. Anecdotal feedback suggested that raising the activity's weight might improve participation, though some students simply found it time-consuming to fully document AI errors.

4.2 Activity 2: Peer Review on Uncovered Topic

Objective: Build both subject-specific knowledge and meta-skills in reviewing AI-based work, with a focus on *transparent documentation* for students of FAMP.

1. Unfamiliar Topic

Students tackled a new concept not yet covered in class, such as an advanced theorem in probability or an emerging cryptographic algorithm. The idea came from Professor Nicola Mazzari², that we warmly thank, during a discussion on Teaching with AI.

2. Use of Chatbot

They consulted Tutor FAMP to gather initial insights, solutions, or proofs, saving all relevant prompts and outputs.

3. Documentation

Each student submitted a file (text or screenshot PDF) via a showing exactly what they typed, plus the responses received from the chatbot.

4. Peer Exchange

Students swapped these files via a workshop peer review activity in Moodle, reviewing each other's AI-driven solutions. The goals included identifying subtle errors, assessing the *quality* of the prompts, and critiquing how students integrated AI outputs.

5. Reflection

Both the original author and the reviewer wrote short reflections on their experience: “How did the chatbot help or hinder understanding of this new concept?” “What did you learn from your peer's usage of the chatbot?”

Participation and Observations. Engagement surpassed that of the Error-Spotting Task, likely due to the interactive nature of peer review. Students reported that seeing classmates' prompts illuminated creative ways to refine their own questions for the chatbot.

5 Academic Integrity and the Evolving Role of AI

5.1 Revisiting Plagiarism

Historically, educators have implemented software (e.g., Turnitin) to detect borrowed text. Yet, detection is growing more complex with AI generative tools. Echoing Eaton (2023), we underscore the necessity of defining new norms around co-authorship

² Department of Mathematics, University of Padova

with AI. The key is not to fear AI but to teach how to document and critically evaluate it—framed as an “AI Literacy” approach.

5.2 Transparency and Reflection

Both activities hinged on transparent documentation of the chatbot’s role. Rather than punish AI usage, we assigned marks for explanations of how students improved or critiqued the AI’s response, along with citations for any text borrowed or reworked from the chatbot. This resonates with the stance of Luiss University, where AI literacy is mandatory, and with the MOOC “Imparare con l’IA” (Sancassani et al., 2023), demonstrating how to safely incorporate AI in helping students learning without compromising academic standards.

6 Detailed Peer Review Rubric

Below is the rubric used for evaluating submissions in the Peer Review Task. Each criterion was assessed at one of four performance levels: Excellent, Good, Sufficient, or Insufficient.

Rubric Usage

- **Usage Clarity:** Did the student articulate *why* they used the chatbot and *how* it contributed (or failed to contribute) to their solution?
- **Critical Thinking:** Did the student evaluate the quality of the AI’s response, identify errors, and demonstrate an understanding of the tool’s strengths/limitations?
- **Integration:** Is the AI-derived material meaningfully merged with the student’s own ideas, or is it merely a superficial paste?
- **Originality:** Does the submission showcase student creativity or personal insight, or is it essentially an AI echo?
- **Documentation & Reflection:** Are the chatbot conversations included (screenshots/links), and does the student offer thoughtful commentary on what worked, what didn’t, and why?

7 Results and Discussion

7.1 Critical AI Literacy Gains

Across both courses, students who fully engaged with the exercises exhibited stronger critical questioning of AI outputs. They reported, for example, being more aware of possible factual gaps, incorrect references, or overconfident “hallucinations.”

7.2 Impact on Academic Integrity

By reframing AI use as a documented, analyzable practice rather than a hidden or forbidden act, the activities aligned with Eaton (2023) in normalizing AI-based writing while still upholding the principle that substantial human cognition and transparency are vital.

7.3 Future Refinements

- **Grading Weight:** Boosting the rubric’s influence on the final course grade might encourage greater participation.
- **Extended Reflection:** Adding a short reflective questionnaire could further tease out how students perceive and interpret AI outputs.
- **Cross-Course Collaboration:** Plans are in motion to replicate these tasks in other fields (e.g., social sciences, humanities) to see if similar patterns emerge.

8 Conclusion

In this paper, we have described two classroom interventions—an Error-Spotting Task and a Peer Review Activity—that leverage a discipline-specific chatbot to cultivate critical AI literacy. Reflecting on longstanding debates around academic integrity, we highlight how transparency in documenting AI usage and active student engagement can help re-envision plagiarism concerns in an age of hybrid writing.

Final Thoughts

- **AI as a Partner, Not an Oracle:** By placing students in the role of “error spotters” and “peer reviewers,” we encourage them to see AI as a fallible but potentially powerful collaborator.

- **Ethical and Accountable Usage:** Echoing the approach of many Universities in the world and guidelines (Unesco (2021), Dede, 2023) , the future of AI in education lies not in strict prohibition but in guiding students to integrate AI responsibly.
- **Scalable Framework:** The two activities described can be adapted to various disciplines, reinforcing a culture of ethical, documented, and reflective AI usage.

Note on Authorship and AI Assistance. The text includes content translated and restructured from an original draft in Italian with the help of ChatGPT. We view such AI involvement as a legitimate editorial tool—akin to grammar checkers or reference managers—provided its contribution is disclosed. The work remains intellectually authored by Marina De Rossi and Carlo Mariconda, consistent with the principle that AI augments (rather than replaces) human scholarship.

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